

The improvement of the accuracy of ship speed through water using a Multi Layered Doppler Sonar (MLDS)

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Abstract. In order to reduce GHG emissions, it is essential to have a correct understanding of the performance of ships in operation, which will feed back into the design of new ships and be used to find optimal routes for ships in operation. One of the most important parameters in performance assessment is ship speed. Due to the influence of tidal currents, a speed through water (STW) rather than a speed over ground (SOG) is usually used in performance analysis. However, the accuracy of measured STW is often questioned. Doppler sonar is often used as a STW meter, but it measures the speed relative to the ship at a given depth, so there is no guarantee that the ship's speed will be measured correctly if the current distribution changes in the depth direction. To overcome this problem, this study attempted to improve the accuracy of STW using Multi-Layered Doppler Sonar (MLDS), which can measure the water speed relative to the ship at multiple water depths. MLDS was installed on six large container ships and the measurement accuracy was compared with that of conventional Single-Layered Doppler Sonar (SLDS). It was confirmed that the MLDS reduced the data variability and performance variation between sister vessels. At the same time, the areas with large differences from the SLDS were shown and compared with the current forecast, which are important in the search for the optimum navigation route.

Keywords: speed through water, STW, Doppler Sonar, MLDS.

1 Introduction

In order to reduce GHG emissions, it is essential to have a correct understanding of the performance of ships in operation. This understanding can feed back into the design of new ships, help determine optimal operational routes, and support decisions on the appropriate timing for hull and propeller cleaning. One of the most important parameters in performance assessment is ship speed. Since ship speed and engine power have a cubic relationship, a 1% error in ship speed leads to approximately a 3% error in power estimation, making accuracy crucial.

Due to the influence of tidal currents, speed through water (STW) is generally used for performance analysis instead of speed over ground (SOG). Among the two commonly used devices for measuring STW—Doppler logs and electromagnetic logs—Doppler logs are regarded as more accurate, as electromagnetic logs measure the flow velocity within the boundary layer and is therefore strongly affected by ship speed, draft, and the condition of hull fouling. For this reason, this study focuses on the use of Doppler logs.

However, the accuracy of measured STW by Doppler logs is often questioned (e.g., [1],[2],[3]). One major source of error is the depth-wise variation in currents. Since Doppler sonar measures the relative speed of the water at a certain depth, it cannot guarantee accurate ship speed measurements when current velocity varies with depth.

Bos [2] clearly identified this issue and proposed an alternative method to determine STW by combining SOG obtained via GPS with forecast currents, instead of measuring STW directly. On the other hand, to address this issue using Doppler sonar, Sudo et al. [4] developed a Multi-Layer Doppler Sonar (MLDS), which can measure flow velocity at multiple layers. They considered two main factors contributing to vertical variation in flow speed: an uneven current profile and disturbances caused by the hull itself. These factors were statistically separated by measuring flow velocity over time. A MLDS was installed on a PCC (Pure Car Carrier), and the depth-wise flow distribution was measured. This distribution was then averaged over time to eliminate temporal variations in current, allowing the extraction of the hull-induced flow distribution. This extracted distribution was then

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compared with CFD simulations, showing good agreement between the measured and simulated results. Based on these results, they proposed a new method for estimating actual ship speed as described in detail in Section 2.

In this study, we applied the method proposed by Sudo et al. [4] to a series of container ships to investigate whether it can improve the accuracy of STW measurement compared to conventional Single-Layered Doppler sonar (SLDS). In addition, the areas with large differences from the SLDS measurements were identified and compared with the current forecasts.

2 Multi-Layered Doppler Sonar (MLDS)

2.1 Measurement principles

Multi-Layered Doppler Sonar (MLDS) was developed by Furuno Electric Co. Ltd. (FURUNO) and MTI Co.Ltd., based on FURUNO's commercial product: model DS-60 [5] with revised signal processing algorithm. As is well known, the principle of Doppler sonar measurement is as follows: a transducer mounted on the bottom of the ship transmits ultrasonic beams and receives the echoes reflected from particles in the water. The frequency of the ultrasonic beam changes in proportion to the relative water velocity along the beam direction—this is known as the Doppler shift. The elapsed time between transmission and reception is directly proportional to the distance between the transducer and the particles. Therefore, by setting an appropriate time interval between transmission and reception, the velocity at a specific depth can be extracted.

In conventional SLDS, velocity can be measured at only a single predefined depth. In contrast, the MLDS incorporates a revised algorithm that allows velocity measurements at multiple arbitrary depths. Although this requires the high measurement accuracy and fast data processing, the DS-60 is capable of meeting these demands. As described in [6], the DS-60 achieves high measurement accuracy by transmitting wideband ultrasonic beams with multiple spectral peaks. It also compensates for the effects of temperature and salinity on underwater sound speed using a phased array transducer [7]. The nominal accuracy of the DS-60 is stated as the greater of $\pm 1.0\%$ or ± 0.1 knots [5].

2.2 Calculation method of the true ship speed proposed Sudo et al. [4]

In a conventional SLDS, a specific water depth must be set, which raises the issue of how to select the most appropriate depth. Since currents vary with depth, setting the measurement depth too deep may result in capturing a relative current velocity that differs from what the ship actually feels. Conversely, if a shallower depth is set, the flow near the hull is affected by disturbances caused by the hull itself. Because an SLDS is usually calibrated during sea trials by comparing with an SOG, inaccurate measurements due to an inappropriate depth setting can result in an incorrect tuning coefficient. This may lead to errors in STW in operation.

To address this issue, Sudo et al. [4] proposed the following method:

1. Measure the relative flow velocity distribution at multiple depths below the hull bottom using an MLDS and normalize them by the relative flow velocity nearest to the hull as shown on the left side of Figure 1.
2. Collect a sufficient amount of data and perform an average analysis by grouping the data according to specific ranges of speed and draft.
3. Calculate the velocity ratio between the deepest and shallowest measurement layers. This ratio is referred to as the "correction factor".
4. Continue collecting correction factors over time until the values converge. In the case shown in Figure 1, the correction factor converged to 1.016 as shown on the right.
5. Estimate the true ship speed by multiplying the measured flow velocity nearest to the hull by the converged correction factor.

This method is based on the assumption that, with a sufficient amount of data averaging, the temporal depth-wise variation in current will converge toward zero. Sudo et al. [4] showed that the histograms of velocity ratios at various depths (relative to the shallowest layer) follow a normal distribution, supporting the validity of this assumption.

Figure 1. Normalized flow velocity by the relative flow velocity closet to the hull (*left*) and the averaged depth-wise flow distribution (*right*) measured on a PCC in Sudo et al. [4].

3 Measurement Results

3.1 Subject ships

The MLDS was installed at the bow of six vessels in a large container ship series (L 399.95 m \times B 61.4 m \times d 16.5 m). As previously mentioned, the MLDS utilizes the same hardware as a conventional SLDS, with only the signal processing algorithm revised. Therefore, it can operate in both SLDS and MLDS modes. To evaluate whether the MLDS improves measurement accuracy, the STW obtained using the conventional SLDS algorithm was compared with that obtained using the newly developed MLDS algorithm.

For these vessels, the SLDS measured flow velocity at a depth of approximately 20 meters, while the MLDS measurements covered a range from 4 meters to 40 meters below the hull bottom. The vessels in this series are identical in both hull form and propeller design. Data was collected over a period of approximately one year after delivery.

3.2 Sea trial

The sea trials for this vessel series were conducted off the coast of Hyuga-nada (east of the Kyushu Peninsula, Japan) between 2023 and 2024. As the monitoring setup was not prepared for the first vessel, the comparative analysis was performed on the remaining five vessels. The sea conditions during the speed/power trials are summarized in Table 1. The speed/power trials were analyzed following the ITTC Recommended Procedure 7.5-04-01-01.1 (2017 version) [8]. The current curves were derived using iterative method.

An example of a current curve for ship E, which experienced the calmest weather conditions, is shown in Figure 2. Assuming that the tidal current curve obtained from the speed/power analysis represents the true current, the discrepancies between the measured currents, i.e. the differences between the SOG and the STW, were investigated. The Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of these differences is shown in Figure 3. As shown, the RMSE values were reduced for all vessels when using the MLDS compared to the conventional SLDS.

An example of the depth-wise distribution of flow velocity measured during the speed/power trials for Ship B is shown in Figure 4. If the current were uniform with depth, the velocity distributions from the double runs would approximately overlap. However, the shape of the distribution differs significantly between the first and second runs during one double run at the same engine output, indicating that the current is depth-dependent and that this distribution changes over time. Although the water depth off Hyuga-nada is sufficiently deep, the current distribution is complex due to the combined influences of the Kuroshio Current and local topographic effects. This complexity can contribute to the differences in the RMSE between the SLDS and MLDS.

An SLDS is usually calibrated after speed/power trials by adjusting a calibration factor based on the average SOG during double runs. The calibration factors vary among ships even in the same series depending on temporal variations in currents, which introduces errors in subsequent measurements in operation.

In contrast, as shown in Table 2, the correction factors of MLDS are almost constant for all the ships, indicating that the system can consistently capture vessel-specific characteristics without influence of depth-dependent variations in current distribution.

Table 1. Weather conditions during sea trials

		ship B	ship C	ship D	ship E	ship F
Wind	m/s	4-6	2-5	4-13	2-5	1-4
Wave (wind)	m	0.3-1.0	0.5	1.5-2.0	0.5	0.5
Wave (swell)	m	1.5	1.5-2	0.5-1.5	0.5	0.5

Figure 2. Current curve analyzed from the sea trial for ship E (*solid line*), and measured current speed obtained by subtracting speed through water from speed over ground for SLDS (*blue circle*) and MLDS (*orange circle*).

Figure 3. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) of current speed for SLDS (*blue*) and MLDS (*orange*) compared with the analytical currents.

Figure 4. Depth-wise distribution of flow velocity measured during the speed/power trials for Ship B. Different colors indicate flow velocities at different engine output settings. Solid symbols represent the flow velocity during the first run, while white symbols represent the second run.

Table 2. Correction factors for sea trial conditions

ship B	ship C	ship D	ship E	ship F
1.024	1.025	1.025	1.025	1.025

3.3 In operation

3.3.1 Monitoring and analysis

Data collection in operation was carried out using the monitoring system Sea-Navi[®] 2.0 developed by Japan Marine United Corporation [9]. The data, sampled at 1 Hz by Voyage Data Recorder (VDR) and statistically processed every ten minutes, was transmitted to the cloud for analysis. Sea-Navi[®] 2.0 incorporates wave nowcast data provided by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA).

To evaluate the performance in operation, the analysis was conducted using the method proposed in the “Project for Evaluation of Ship Performance in Actual Seas – Japan Maritime Cluster Collaborative Research” (OCTARVIA Project) [10]. A key feature of this method is its unique filtering approach for external force to accurately evaluate calm-sea performance by utilizing as much data as possible. This approach is referred to as Resistance Criteria Method (RCM). The filtering method is described in detail in [10], and briefly outlined below:

1. Data is filtered for steady state based on the criteria shown in Table 3. Here, N_E represents the engine revolution, β the drift angle and δ the rudder angle.

Table 3. Filtering criteria for steady state [10]

Item	N_E	$ \beta $ [deg.]	$ \delta $ [deg.]	$ STW - SOG $ [knots]
Criteria	Over 40% of N_{EMCR}	3.0	5.0	0.5

2. Data is extracted within 5% of the representative displacement. Ship speed is corrected based on the Admiralty coefficient.
3. Data is filtered by apparent slip ratio within the standard deviation.
4. Data is filtered by the increase rate of added resistance due to winds and waves, $\delta R = (R_{ms} - R_{id}) / R_{id}$, where R_{ms} represents the total resistance in actual seas and R_{id} the resistance in still water. Performance curve in

a calm sea is obtained using the evaluation index $EI = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \{d_{norm}(i)\}}{N}}$, where d_{norm} , illustrated in Figure 5, is the normal distance between each data point and the fitting curve.

Figure 5. Outline of the filtering method and the definition of d_{norm} used in the evaluation index. [10]

The filtering criteria related to the difference between SOG and STW in Table 3, as well as the apparent slip ratio, are based on the assumption that STW is inaccurate. However, since the purpose of this study is to assess the improvement in STW accuracy, these criteria were not applied. The other criteria were the same as those used in [10]. The added resistance due to wind and that due to waves were calculated using a regression formula [11] and a theoretical method with an empirical correction [12], respectively, following the same approach as in [10]. Data for ship C were unavailable due to an unknown error in data transfer.

3.3.2 Scatter of speed/power relations

As an example of the speed-power curves obtained using the method mentioned above, the curves based on SOG, STW by SLDS and STW by MLDS are shown in Figure 6. For reference, a curve based on STW by SLDS using the original filtering conditions in [10], which consider the difference between SOG and STW and the apparent slip ratio, is also shown in the same figure. Figure 7 shows the Evaluation Index (EI) for each curve across five ships with the same representative displacement. The order of EI representing the scatter in the speed-power relationship is the same for all the ships: $SOG > SLDS > MLDS > SLDS$ with the original filtering conditions. As expected, the scatter can be reduced by using MLDS compared to SLDS. Although applying the original filtering conditions to SLDS can more effectively reduce the scatter, it should be noted that they also decrease the number of data points available for analysis by approximately half.

Figure 8 shows ratios of the difference in brake power at a ship speed of 16 knots, a frequent speed in operation, to the mean brake power across five ships with the same representative displacement. Since the vessels are identical in hull and propeller design and their construction quality was controlled to the same standard, the ratio should theoretically have a similar value. Of course, they cannot be the same due to other sources of error, though, such as difference in wave height between actual conditions and nowcast. In this regard, MLDS is better than SLDS. The variance in the ratio for MLDS is the smallest within 1-2%, which is reduced almost half from 2-3% of SLDS.

From the above, it can be said that MLDS is superior to SLDS for representing the STW.

Figure 6. Power curves for ship A base on speed over ground, SOG, (*upper left*), speed through water using SLDS (*upper right*), MLDS (*lower left*) and SLDS with the original filtering condition (*lower right*). Solid line, red circles and blue circles represents fitting curve, filtering data and evaluation data, respectively.

Figure 7. Evaluation Index (EI) of SOG (*black*), SLDS (*blue*), MLDS (*orange*) and SLDS with the original filtering condition (*gray, dots*).

Figure 8. Ratio of the difference in brake power at a ship speed of 16 knots to the mean brake power across five ships, shown for SOG (black), SLDS (blue), MLDS (orange) and SLDS with the original filtering condition (gray, dots).

3.3.3 Areas with large differences in STW between SLDS and MLDS

The difference in STW between SLDS and MLDS for ship F is shown in Figure 9. Red areas indicate where the STW by MLDS is faster than that by SLDS, while blue areas indicate where it is slower. Larger differences are observed closer to the shore, which is understandable, as seen in the sea trials conducted off Hyūga-nada.

To further investigate what happened in these areas, data from the period of July 10-13, 2024, during the vessel's passage off the west coast of Africa as shown in dotted circle in Figure 9, were examined. Figure 10 shows propeller revolutions with contours of absolute wind speed, ship speed (SOG, STW by SLDS and STW by MLDS), and current speed, i.e., the difference between STW and SOG, based on SLDS and MLDS and nowcast. the contours overlaid on propeller revolutions represent absolute wind speed, with blue indicating weak winds. On July 11-12, the propeller revolutions were steady, and the wind was very weak. Thus, the ship speed should have remained constant. However, the SOG and the STW by SLDS showed sudden fluctuations, while the STW by MLDS remained stable. Examining the depth-wise distribution of flow velocity, shown at the bottom of Figure 10, it was found that the direction of the flow suddenly changed. This caused the unnatural change observed in the STW by SLDS.

Similar to the sea trial area, abrupt variations in depth-wise flow distribution tend to occur near the coastlines, suggesting that the error in STW can become significantly larger in such areas. In areas where the difference between SOG and STW changes rapidly, it is recommended that such data be filtered out when using STW by SLDS for analysis.

Figure 9. Voyage map with contours showing the difference in STW between SLDS and MLDS for ship F.

Figure 10. Time history from: propeller speed with contours of absolute wind speed, ship speed - SOG (black), SLDS (blue) and MLDS (orange), and current speed based on forecast (black), SLDS (blue) and MLDS (orange), from the top. The lowest figure shows depth-wise flow speed distribution measured by MLDS at 2:00 11/7/2024 (gray), at 18:00 2024/7/11 (red), and at 2:00 12/7/2024 (green).

3.3.4 Correction factor

In the MLDS, ship speed is calculated by multiplying the measured flow velocity nearest to the hull by a correction factor. Therefore, the accuracy of the correction factor directly influences the accuracy of the ship speed estimation. Figure 11 shows an example of measured correction factors for a group with a 3-meter draft and a ship speed of 3 knots. The correction factors estimated using the CFD solver SURF [13] are also shown in the same figure for comparison. Both the measurements and the CFD results show the same trend: the correction factor tends to increase with deeper drafts and higher speeds. While the measured correction factors are generally about 1% higher than those estimated by the CFD, the similarity in trends suggests that the correction factors were reasonably obtained. Table 4 shows the correction factors within the red box in Figure 11, where the most frequent draft–speed combination in operation, across the five ships. Since the correction factors for all ships are nearly constant, it can be concluded that the correction factors obtained using MLDS are consistent and reasonable.

Figure 12 shows an example of the convergence of the correction factors. Although the values fluctuate significantly at first, they start to stabilize after approximately 500 data points, which correspond to about half a week, considering data are collected every ten minutes as previously mentioned. A major drawback of MLDS is that correction factors cannot be obtained for draft–speed combinations where sufficient data are not available. This issue needs to be addressed using alternative methods, such as interpolation based on CFD results.

Figure 11. Correction factors by CFD (left) and measurement for ship A(right).

Table 4. Measured correction factor within the red box in Figure 11

ship A	ship B	ship D	ship E	ship F
1.043	1.044	1.045	1.046	1.047

Figure 12. Time history of correction factors for ship A.

4 Current forecast

Weather routing is a widely used technology for ensuring safe voyages and reducing greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Its importance has been growing recently, particularly with the increased focus on wind-assisted propulsion systems. Maximizing the use of weather routing is expected to play a key role in achieving net-zero GHG emissions. In this context, the accuracy of tidal current predictions becomes critical. Currents can be harnessed as a source of natural energy, with a potential impact of ± 2 knots—equivalent to approximately 30–40% of the ship's brake power. Effectively utilizing these currents presents a significant challenge for the maritime industry.

The monitoring system Sea-Navi[®] 2.0 incorporates the SMOC (Surface Merged Ocean Current) from the Copernicus service provided by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts [14]. The comparison between the measured currents and the forecast is shown in Figure 13. The forecast current shows positive correlation with the measurement based on both SLDS and MLDS. Figure 14 shows the mean and the standard deviation of difference in current speed between forecast and measurement. MLDS shows a slightly better correlation with the forecast. Although the standard deviation of about 0.5 knots is not negligible and how much accuracy is needed for a captain to trust and use the weather routing, the mathematical current forecast captures the trends well.

Figure 15 shows the difference in current speed between the forecast and the measurement by MLDS for ship A. As shown in this figure, it is difficult to identify where the deviation in the forecast and the measurement is large. However, depth-wise current profiles collected globally from many ships can serve as valuable input to improve forecast accuracy, and in this sense, MLDS has the potential to contribute significantly to enhancing future tidal current predictions.

Figure 13. Comparison of forecast current speed and measurement based on SLDS (left) and MLDS (right) for ship A.

Figure 14. Mean (left) and standard deviation (right) of difference in current speed between forecast and measurement by SLDS (blue) and MLDS (orange).

Figure 15. Voyage map with contours showing the differences in current speed between the forecast and the measurement based on MLDS for ship A.

5 Conclusion

Accurately measuring ship speed is crucial for reliable ship performance analysis. In order to improve the conventional Single-Layered Doppler Sonar (SLDS), Multi-Layered Doppler Sonar (MLDS), which can measure the water speed relative to the ship at multiple water depths, has been developed as described in detail in [4]. In this study, the accuracy of MLDS was evaluated. MLDS was installed on six vessels in a large container ship series. Based on data from the sea trial and in operation, the following findings were confirmed:

- When the tidal current curve derived from speed/power analysis is assumed to represent the true current, the currents measured using MLDS were consistently closer to those derived from the speed/power analysis across all vessels than those using SLDS.
- When the onboard monitoring data were analyzed by Resistance Criteria Method proposed in the OCTARVIA Project, both data variability and performance variation between sister vessels were reduced when MLDS was used instead of SLDS.
- From the observation both during sea trials and in operation, the differences in the STW between MLDS and SLDS tended to occur where the depth-wise current distribution changed rapidly over short periods. They are likely to occur near coastlines.
- Temporal variations in depth-wise current can be eliminated with a sufficient amount of data averaging. Consequently, the velocity ratio between the deepest and shallowest measurement layers - referred to as the correction factor, which represents flow disturbances caused by the hull - can be extracted. Consistent and reasonable values of STW can be estimated using these correction factors.
- Conversely, a major drawback of MLDS is that correction factors cannot be obtained for draft-speed combinations where sufficient data are not available. This issue needs to be addressed using alternative methods, such as interpolation based on CFD results.
- The current forecast provided by the Copernicus service can well capture the trends in the measurement.

The accurate measurement of STW is essential not only for conventional performance analysis, but also for the assessment of the new technologies validated by short-term “on-off” tests, such as wind assisted propulsion systems [15] and air lubrication systems. In this regard, MLDS is expected to be widely utilized. Furthermore, collecting global depth-wise current profiles from many ships equipped with MLDS has the potential to significantly enhance future tidal current prediction accuracy.

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